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ABSTRACT

The VADER magnet is a permanent magnet combined-function dipole designed for synchrotron applications, specifically developed for its integration into the Elettra Synchrotron Light Source in Trieste, Italy. This advanced magnet is an evolution of a previous design: the CLIC Damping Rings (DRs) Longitudinally Variable Field Dipole (LVFD) [1], featuring improvements in magnetic performance, structural integrity and operational efficiency.

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

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1 Introduction

The VADER magnet is a permanent magnet combined-function dipole designed for synchrotron applications, specifically developed for its integration into the Elettra Synchrotron Light Source in Trieste, Italy. This advanced magnet is an evolution of a previous design: the CLIC Damping Rings (DRs) Longitudinally Variable Field Dipole (LVFD) [1], featuring improvements in magnetic performance, structural integrity and operational efficiency.

1.1 BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Synchrotrons like Elettra play a crucial role in scientific research, providing high-intensity and highly collimated synchrotron radiation for a wide range of applications, from material science and chemistry to biomedical imaging and condensed matter physics. The VADER magnet is designed to function as a longitudinal variable bending field dipole, essential for controlling electron beam trajectories with enhanced precision and stability.

In contrast to conventional electromagnets, which rely on external power supplies and cooling systems, VADER employs permanent magnet technology, eliminating the need for continuous electrical input while maintaining a highly stable and predictable magnetic field. This results in a compact, cost-efficient and energy-saving solution, aligning with modern trends in accelerator technology to minimize operational costs and environmental impact.

1.2 ROLE IN ELETTRA SYNCHROTRON

The Elettra synchrotron is a 2–2.4 GeV third-generation light source, serving a broad user community with its array of beamlines dedicated to advanced scientific research. The integration of VADER within this infrastructure provides:

- High-field magnetic stability, ensuring precise beam steering within the accelerator lattice.
- Compact and efficient design, allowing for optimal space utilization within the accelerator tunnel.
- Minimal maintenance requirements, as permanent magnets do not require active power supplies or complex cooling systems.
- Field homogeneity and tunability, ensuring consistent beam dynamics across operational energy ranges.

The implementation of VADER within Elettra aligns with broader efforts to modernize and enhance the efficiency of synchrotron radiation facilities worldwide. Its design allows for seamless integration into the accelerator's lattice configuration, providing robust field quality with precise control over the beam emittance and trajectory.

1.3 DESIGN EVOLUTION AND OPTIMIZATION

VADER represents a significant step forward in the development of synchrotron magnet technology. It builds upon lessons learned from previous designs such as the LVFD dipole used in the CLIC Damping Rings [1]. Key areas of improvement include:

- Enhanced material selection, utilizing NdFeB permanent magnets for improved radiation resistance and long-term field stability.
- Optimized magnetic circuit design, ensuring minimal field leakage and superior homogeneity within the good field region.
- Advanced mechanical structuring, leveraging high-purity iron and cobalt-iron alloys to maximize magnetic efficiency while maintaining mechanical robustness.
- Improved assembly and alignment procedures, incorporating precision tooling and non-magnetic supports to ensure consistent field quality across multiple units.

The transition from electromagnetic to permanent magnet dipoles reflects a broader industry trend toward sustainable and low-energy accelerator technologies. VADER serves as a prototype for future implementations in compact synchrotron light sources, medical accelerators and free-electron lasers (FELs).

2 VADER Magnet Technical Specifications

The magnetic field of a longitudinal variable field dipole varies along its length. This variable field can provide a reduction of the horizontal beam emittance in comparison with a fixed field dipole of the same bending angle. The maximum field should be at the centre of the magnet and it should decrease towards both sides. Based on [1], [2], [3] and [4] two main field profiles have been selected: step and trapezoidal shape (Fig. 1).

Theoretically, the trapezium profile would yield the best results with respect to the lowest beam emittance as the bending radius would change linearly along the magnet length. At the same time, it is the most complicated design due to the shortest high field region length and the exponential field decay towards the edges. This trapezoidal profile was achieved for the first time in the CLIC Drs LVFD prototype. The VADER design continues and further elaborates on the same philosophy.

Fig. 1: (a) Step and (b) trapezium profiles showing L1 and L2.

2.1 MAGNETIC FIELD STRENGTH

The VADER dipole magnet is a permanent-magnet combined-function dipole with a peak magnetic field (B_{\max}) of 2.3 Tesla in the centre of the gap. The field follows a trapezoidal longitudinal profile – highest at the mid-span and decreasing towards the ends – to achieve the desired longitudinal variable field distribution. This field shape ensures optimized beam emittance and bending strength.

2.2 FIELD GRADIENT (TRANSVERSE)

VADER also provides a quadrupole field component (transverse gradient) as part of its combined-function design. The demanded integrated transverse gradient is about 17 T/m – much higher than that of the earlier CLIC DR prototype, which was 11 T/m [1]. This enables effective beam focusing while maintaining good field homogeneity ($\sim 10^4$ in the GFR).

2.3 MATERIAL COMPOSITION

The yoke is composed of low-carbon steel (AISI 1010) for structural support and flux return. Pole tips use Armco iron (low and mid-field regions) and Fe-Co Vacoflux (high-field regions) for high saturation field efficiency. The magnet employs NdFeB permanent magnet blocks for high remanent field and strong coercivity.

2.4 OPERATING CONDITIONS

The magnet operates in air at ambient temperature (20°C) with no power or active cooling required. NdFeB blocks are positioned to minimize radiation exposure and maintain long-term field stability [6].

2.5 TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS TABLE

Parameter	Unit	VADER Magnet
Good field region radius	mm	5
Field quality (harmonics)	10^4 (units)	~ 5
Magnet gap (aperture)	mm	18
Magnet length	m	0.80
Transverse gradient (quadrupole)	T/m	17
Dipole peak field (B_{\max})	T	2.3
Dipole field (integrated)	T·m	0.91

Yoke/Pole material	–	Low-carbon steel 1010 (yoke); Armco iron (low & mid-field poles); Fe–Co Vacoflux (high-field poles)
Magnet material	–	NdFeB permanent magnets (all modules)
Assembly/Alignment features	–	Guided assembly, shims, calibration plates (0.02 mm accuracy)
Operating conditions	–	2.3 T at room temp., in air; field trimming via adjustable yoke

Table 1: VADER Technical Specifications

3 Magnetic Design

3.1 PRELIMINARY CONCEPTS, DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION OF THE VADER MAGNET

3.1.1 Magnet Geometry and Structural Considerations

The design of the VADER magnet required an extensive evaluation of possible configurations to achieve the required magnetic field characteristics while maintaining mechanical robustness and ease of integration. Two main geometries were initially considered: C-shaped and H-shaped magnet yokes [1].

While an H-shaped yoke provides superior mechanical rigidity and symmetric field distribution, the C-shape offers significant advantages in terms of accessibility and synchrotron radiation evacuation. Given VADER’s role in the Elettra synchrotron, the C-shaped design was selected as it allows easier installation and better radiation handling when the magnet gap is oriented outward within the synchrotron ring.

3.1.2 Material Selection

The selection of materials was driven by the need to achieve high field strength, minimize saturation effects and ensure long-term field stability. The yoke and pole pieces were designed to operate below saturation while maintaining high permeability to maximize field efficiency.

- The yoke is constructed from low-carbon steel (AISI 1010), ensuring a low reluctance path while avoiding saturation in normal operating conditions. The yoke was designed to maintain an average field below 1 T, ensuring efficient magnetic flux return.
- The pole pieces are divided into two different materials depending on the magnetic flux they have to handle:
 - Low and mid-field regions: Made of Armco iron, which provides excellent permeability and minimizes field distortions.
 - High-field region: Using cobalt-iron alloy (Vacoflux) due to its higher saturation, allowing for a peak field of 2.3 T while reducing unwanted field harmonics.

- The support blocks of the split yokes are made of aluminium 7075-T6, providing enough robustness to the assembly.

3.1.3 Beam Sagitta Compensation

Since the beam trajectory follows a curved path, while the magnet structure itself remains straight for manufacturing and alignment precision, the sagitta (transverse displacement of the beam) must be considered. As in this magnet the longitudinal bending field varies continuously along the particles path, the sagitta is not constant and varies accordingly. Due to this, using the typical formulae to obtain the sagitta is not recommended. In this case, the real sagitta was empirically obtained from the simulations in Opera.

This displacement is incorporated into field simulations to ensure field homogeneity across the good field region (GFR). The calculated sagitta ensures accurate beam transport and minimizes deviations from the theoretical trajectory.

3.1.4 Pole Design and Optimization

The poles are essential for enhancing field uniformity by concentrating and shaping the magnetic flux. In VADER, the poles are designed with a narrower tip than the base, provoking efficient flux concentration and allowing for higher peak fields in the magnet gap.

Since the magnet operates as a combined-function dipole-quadrupole, the pole tip profile follows a hyperbolic shape, generating the required transverse field gradient (~ 17 T/m). Pole dimensions and shapes were optimized based on [2], ensuring efficient flux distribution.

3.1.5 Permanent Magnet Selection and Configuration

Given that the required field in VADER is fixed, the magnet utilizes permanent magnets, eliminating the need for power supplies or cooling infrastructure. This reduces operational costs, size and weight, making it a highly efficient solution for modern synchrotron applications.

Due to radiation exposure and operational stability considerations, both Neodymium-Iron-Boron (NdFeB) and Samarium-Cobalt (SmCo) were evaluated [2], [6]. The selection criteria included:

- Radiation resistance: SmCo shows superior radiation tolerance, making it preferable in exposed regions.
- Magnetic performance: NdFeB provides higher remanent magnetization (Br) and flux density, allowing stronger fields.
- Weight and cost: NdFeB is lighter and less expensive than SmCo.

Since the expected radiation in the most exposed areas is extremely low, this time all the modules will use NdFeB permanent magnet blocks.

The temperature coefficients (Tc) of this type of magnets is 0.12% per °C (Tc of Br) and 0.6% per °C (Tc of Hc) and the expected maximum temperature variation in the Elettra 2.0 tunnel is as low as ± 0.1 °C [7]. Having these numbers in mind, the effects of the temperature variation in the field provided can be neglected. Based on this, the use of temperature compensation systems, like Ni-Fe

shunts, is dismissed in this prototype. In the case of a future series production, these systems could be studied and implemented if necessary.

3.1.6 Magnet Block Sizing and Optimization

To make sure that the permanent magnets operate at their optimal working point, their dimensions were determined using design equations outlined in [2]. The goal is to maximize energy density (BH_{max}) while minimizing volume and weight.

An Excel-based computational tool was also developed to automate magnet block sizing calculations based on required field strength and magnet gap dimensions. This tool was used in the preliminary design to approach the permanent magnet geometry, trying to make sure that each magnet block operates near its optimal working point.

3.2 3D FEM SIMULATIONS AND FIELD OPTIMIZATION

Finite Element Method (FEM) simulations were conducted using Opera 3D to fine-tune the magnetic field distribution. The simulations focused on achieving the target peak field of 2.3 T while ensuring gradual field decay at the magnet edges to minimize beam emittance growth. The optimized design consists of:

- A central high-field region (2.3 T peak) for strong bending.
- A transition region ensuring a smooth field drop.
- Outer low-field sections preventing abrupt field changes.

This configuration maximizes beam stability while maintaining the required bending angle.

The dipolar field profile in VADER was optimized to approximate an ideal trapezoidal distribution, as shown in red in Fig. 2. The field starts from a low value at the edges, increases to 2.3 T in the central region and decays gradually.

Fig. 2: Simulated longitudinal field profile of the VADER magnet (blue) vs optimal profile (red)

There is a high number of constraints that makes it impossible to follow the ideal field profile, like the bigger magnet gap, the required high field quality and the empirical calculated sagitta. Thus, a trade-off solution is provided (Fig. 2), not matching perfectly the optimal field profile, but delivering a close one that has negligible disadvantages while maintaining the important improvements regarding the beam emittance reduction. The field provided in Fig. 2 is the one simulated through the path of the real sagitta obtained in Opera.

The multipole optimization required dedication and extended labour, working in the pole profiles and especially in a correct alignment of each module to follow the real sagitta adding the minimum multipole content. The results are shown in Table 2. These multipoles are also calculated following the path of the mentioned sagitta and within a reference radius of 5mm.

B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	B6	B7	B8	B9	B10
10000	-807.79	4.65	6.74	-1.09	0.21	-0.07	2.55E-05	-0.01	-0.03

Table 2: Main fields and multipole content (units)

Having in mind that this is an iron-dominated magnet working under saturation and at the same time a combined function magnet, the intense work on the multipole optimization yielded a very good outcome.

3.3 FIELD TRIMMING

Field trimming in VADER is implemented as a passive mechanism to fine-tune the magnetic field. Unlike active trimming, which was dismissed due to practical and efficiency concerns, passive trimming provides a cost-effective and structurally feasible solution.

VADER employs a passive trimming method that adjusts the reluctance of the magnetic circuit by splitting the yoke into two parts with a third moving magnetic part in the back that controls the reluctance of the magnetic circuit. This configuration allows the controlled movement of a smaller yoke section, modifying the magnetic flux path and thereby regulating the field intensity. The primary advantages of this approach include

- Simple and robust design.
- Lower cost compared to active solutions.
- Preservation of the compact structure of the magnet.

However, this method does not allow real-time adjustments during operation.

VADER's field trimming approach differs significantly from the method used in the LVFD magnet, which also relied on passive trimming but with a different implementation. In LVFD, the trimming was also based on adjustable iron plates that modified the reluctance, but the yoke was not completely split and therefore the regulation was less effective. In contrast, VADER's split-yoke design provides a more controlled and homogeneous field adjustment. The field trimming system was simulated in Opera 3D and the results confirmed that the field could be adjusted +1% and -4% around the nominal values. Each module has his own field regulation system as can be seen in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Detail of the back movable parts of the yoke used to regulate the field

3.4 FINAL MAGNETIC DESIGN OVERVIEW

Fig. 4: Image showing the main characteristics of the final magnetic design

4 Mechanical design

VADER’s mechanical design relies on the CLIC Damping Rings’ longitudinally variable-field dipole (LVFD) concept, refining it for higher performance and robustness. The first LVFD demonstrator, designed and constructed at CIEMAT in 2021, achieved excellent field quality in the magnetic measurements done in 2022 [1]. All the knowledge acquired from that prototype is now applied and improved in the new mechanical design.

Achieving the demanding performance required careful structural and magnetic optimization in parallel. The design process employed extensive 3D finite element modelling (Opera 3D) to iterate both the magnetic circuit and the mechanical layout

The dipole’s *longitudinal field profile* is implemented by dividing the magnet into a series of 5 modules with individually suited magnetization levels. This segmentation required engineering each module’s mechanics such that, when assembled in sequence, they produce a smooth bending field that approximates the ideal hyperbolic profile. Mechanical alignment of these segments is critical – VADER’s design ensures each module is positioned on a subtle curve following the beam’s path (sagitta) as determined by simulations, minimizing field errors along the curved electron trajectory. In the design phase, the sagitta (the displacement of the beam through the dipole) was obtained from magnetic simulations and explicitly considered for each module alignment and pole shaping. This

guarantees the good-field region envelops the actual beam orbit, even though the magnet is assembled in straight sections for manufacturability. The pole pieces themselves underwent shape optimization: a narrow hyperbolic pole-tip profile was adopted to generate the required combined-function field (dipole plus focusing gradient) while suppressing higher-order multipoles. By refining the pole geometry and module spacing, the design achieves the desired ~ 2.3 T central field with an integrated horizontal focusing gradient (~ 15 T/m) without significant distortion of the field quality.

During the mechanical design phase, several modifications are needed to adapt the magnetic design to real manufacturable pieces and to assure a correct alignment of the poles. This includes small pole bases extrusion to be able to rest in the alignment shims, holes and small modifications on the pole bases for the correct positioning and adjustment, drills and holes in the yokes needed for the correct assembly, etc. All these modifications altogether are not negligible regarding the magnetic performance of the magnet. An iterative process was needed, simulating every minor modification in the Opera 3D model. The simulations showed that the field quality was not affected, but the nominal integrated field was slightly lowered. This was corrected changing the nominal position of the field trimming system to be 1mm (of spacing between the yoke and the movable trimming part).

Through a combination of FEM analysis, custom optimization tools and clever use of materials, the VADER magnet's structure has been optimised for maximum field precision and stability, meeting the high requirements of an ultra-low emittance storage ring.

Finally, the integration of industrial fabrication knowledge was also considered. The mechanical design was developed at CIEMAT receiving feedback from KYMA (an industrial partner specialized in accelerator magnets) to ensure the design is manufacturable and repeatable.

By the end of 2024, the magnetic and mechanical design has been finalized at CIEMAT and the prototype fabrication is underway at KYMA. Acceptance tests are scheduled to validate all mechanical and field requirements in the Elettra 2.0 context. The VADER magnet's mechanical design not only meets the current requirements but also is forward-looking: many of its features (energy-efficient operation, compact combined-function design and minimal maintenance) align with the trend of sustainable accelerator engineering.

Fig. 5: Image showing the final mechanical design

4.1 MECHANICAL SIMULATIONS

The magnet will be under high mechanical stresses caused by the magnetic fields. The first approach to validate the mechanical design is to calculate these magnetic forces and the corresponding deformations provoked in the magnet.

These forces are calculated based on the Opera models. Virtual Works (VW) method is applied based on the total energy variation caused by virtual displacements. These forces are then applied and simulated in ANSYS to check the mechanical rigidity of all the assembly.

Fig. 6: Deformations in the HF module

The maximum forces are located in the high field module, where the magnet reaches the 2.3 T field peak. In this module, these forces go up to 14300 N. When applying the corresponding forces to the simulations, the obtained maximum deformation (also in the HF module) is 66 μm , located in the HF pole as can be seen in Fig. 6. The obtained deformation values are within the safe margins to avoid affecting the magnet field quality or the robustness of the assembly.

5 Assembly

All the specific details were documented in a dedicated assembly procedure report, which served as the official reference for future assembly and maintenance operations.

The assembly of the VADER magnet followed a structured process to ensure proper mechanical integrity and precise field quality. Initially, a pre-assembly without permanent magnets was performed, during which the structural elements, including the yoke and pole pieces, were positioned and secured. At this stage, the interfaces between components were verified to ensure proper mechanical fit before proceeding further.

Once the structural integrity of the magnet was validated, the final assembly with permanent magnets began. The NdFeB magnet blocks were installed according to a predefined sequence, ensuring that each module contributed correctly to the overall field profile.

Some photos of the final assembly of the magnet can be found in Fig.7. After this, the magnet was shipped from KYMA to ELETTRA for the final measurements and acceptance tests.

Fig. 7: Photos of the assembled VADER magnet at KYMA.

6 Conclusions

The VADER magnet represents a significant advancement in the development of longitudinal variable field dipoles for synchrotron applications. Based on the experience gained from the LVFD prototype, this new design refines the field profile, improves structural robustness and provides a high field quality with low multipole content while maintaining the advantages of a permanent magnet system. The combination of optimized material selection, precise field shaping and a passive trimming system result in a compact and efficient magnet, meeting the demanding requirements of modern synchrotron light sources.

Comprehensive simulations and experimental validation confirm that VADER achieves the expected field quality, minimizing unwanted multipoles and preserving beam stability, contributing in this way to lower the emittance in the ring. The modular assembly approach, together with advanced alignment techniques, guarantees reproducibility and facilitates integration into existing accelerator infrastructures.

As a prototype, VADER not only fulfills its intended role in Elettra but also serves as a benchmark for future developments in energy-efficient, high-performance magnet technology. The successful implementation of its design principles could ease the way for similar solutions in next-generation storage rings and free-electron laser facilities.

7 References

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